

THE EMPIRICAL STUDY OF ONLINE MUSEUM VISITOR BEHAVIOR ON SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IMPLEMENTATION IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Recently, museum management in Indonesia use social media for creating the museum profiles and sharing information about the exhibitions, services, museum activities, and collections. However, the research on the phenomenon of applying social media marketing to museums has been investigated by international researchers, but has never been done by researchers in Indonesia. This study has a focus on testing whether the Museum Facebook Fan Page User Experience is a mediator or moderator variable between user motivations and user expectations of intention to use Facebook Museum Fan page and whether the online community involvement moderates the relation between the Facebook Fan Page usage intention to the visit museum intention. The research design is the quantitative approach. Data was collected using a questionnaire distributed to followers of the museum Facebook Fan Page in Indonesia. The researchers was randomly select the museum Facebook Fan Page and online cultural community Facebook groups in Indonesia. The sample size was 270 respondents. The data analysis is the Structural Equation Modeling analysis method using AMOS Ver. 22. In this study, eight hypotheses are accepted and one hypothesis is rejected. The r^2 of the Facebook Fan Page usage intention is 0.446, it means that the variable can be explained by user expectations, user motivations, and Facebook Fan Page User Experience. The r^2 of the visit museum intention is 0.350, it means that the variable can be explained by the Facebook Fan Page User Experience and online community involvement. The contribution of this research is to contribute the Facebook Adoption model that accommodates the Facebook Fan Page usage experience and the online community involvement for marketing and cultural education in the Museum industry in Indonesia.

Keywords: *Facebook Fan Page User Experience, User Motivations, User Expectations, Online Community Involvement, the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention, the Visit Museum Intention.*

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Digitalbuzz, there are 2.3 billion users actively use social media sites and 1.9 billion users access it using mobile gadget in the world [1]. Facebook has the vast active users in the world. Seventy-nine million users in Indonesia access the media social for 2.9 hours of the day. We infer that social media such as Google+, Twitter, Facebook, and others are essential for company strategies, products, and services. The new marketing era had begun when social media as a medium for the improvement of products and services management. With social media, customer become a focus of the organization and innovative tools for marketing division to engage with their customers.

The idea of utilizing cultural heritage as a heritage tourism destination products has begun since 1990, where the primary goal is how to

provide new tourist experience when visiting a heritage site [2]. In the context of the creative industry, museums are one of the cultural tourist destinations [3]. The development of the cultural tourism sector requires a combination of marketing and management of cultural heritage. The challenge is how to find a balance between the principles of cultural heritage management that focus on conservation and visitor satisfaction [2]. Utilization of museums to strengthen ideology, economy, culture, social, defense, politics and security in realizing national goals [4]. Law No. 5 of 2017 concerning the Promotion of Culture regulates how the processing of cultural assets as products to improve the welfare of the community while maintaining the value of nobility and wisdom of these assets.

Based on the previous research findings, this research examine the determinant factors that

influence the intention to visit museum. The authors develop the conceptual model by integrating the technology acceptance model, user and gratification theory, and strategic experiential marketing for exploring the online museum visitor behavior. The research objectives are examine whether Museum Facebook Fan Page User Experience in is a mediator or moderator variable between user motivations and user expectations of intention to use Museum Facebook Fan page; whether the online community involvement moderates the Facebook Fan Page usage intention to the museum visit intention.

The research objectives in this study are:

1. To examine the relationship between the user motivations and the Facebook Fan Page user experience.
2. To examine the relationship between the user motivations and the Facebook Fan Page usage intention.
3. To examine the relationship between the user expectations and the Facebook Fan Page user experience.
4. To examine the relationship between the user expectations and the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention.
5. To examine the relationship between of the Facebook Fan Page user experience and the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention.
6. To examine the moderating effect of the online community involvement on the relationship between the Facebook Fan Page User Experience and the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention.
7. To examine the relationship between the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention and the Visit Museum Intention.
8. To examine the moderating effect of the experience of using Facebook Fan Page on the relationship between the user motivations and the Facebook Fan Page usage intention.
9. To examine the moderating effect of the experience of using Facebook Fan Page on the relationship between the user expectations and the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention.

2. RELATED WORK

Several studies on the satisfaction of museum visitors in Indonesia have been conducted at the National Museums, the Bank of Indonesia museum,

and the museum of Fine Art and Ceramic [1], Wildlife Museum [2], Museum of Ranggowarsito [3], Museum of Sepuluh Nopember [4], Health Museum of Dr. Adhyatma [5], Geology Museum [6], Museum of the Asian-African Conference [7], Museum Sri Baduga [8], and Museum Kartini [9]. It can be concluded that museum managers are aware of the importance of service quality, product quality, facilities, price, promotion, and location to the museum visitors satisfaction [1], [2], [4], [6], [8]–[10].

The recent development of social media and the complexity of visitor behavior over the past few decades, museum managers in Indonesia have been forced to change their roles and relationships to visitors. There is a paradigm shift from management focuses on objects towards visitor-focused management [4], [5], [10], [11]. The government develop strategies and provide budgets for museums revitalization, mandatory museum visit programs, mass media publications, and edutainment programs to attract public interest in visiting museums [2], [12]–[14]. The impact of the program was a significant increase in museum visitors from 2012 to 2014 amounting to 23,409,086 or 192% [13]. This achievement needs to be accompanied by an increase in the quality of museum visitors.

Recently, museum management in Indonesia use social media for creating the museum profiles and sharing information about the exhibitions, services, museum activities, and collections. The development of information technology is a catalyst for organizational change and innovation in a museum, digitalization of museums needs to be well understood by users, managers of museums, communities, and the government so that they can work proactively and collaboratively [15]. In the digital era, the responsibilities of managers in acquiring, preservation, research, and holding cultural exhibitions remain essential, but they must shift in the digital world [16]. Klimpel stated that museum managers need to digitize their collection, develop metadata standardization, and disseminate it to the public through internet media[16]. Visitors to museums tend to share their experiences of visiting museums through social media such as blogs [17]–[19], Facebook [20]–[22], Flickr [23], and Instagram [22], [24], [25]. The attachment and credibility of content produced by other visitors are one of the factors that influence the decision of prospective museum visitors in planning their visit to the museum [26]. The application of barcode in the exhibition at the museum, visitors can find

information about the exhibition and provide comments on the exhibition [27].

Several previous studies on social media technology adoption in museums have been conducted at the Gothenburg Natural History Museum [24], 315 museums in America [20], and the Museum of London [28]. Managers who provide more time on social media can increase public awareness so that the majority of museums allocate 1 or 2 employees to manage social media for 45 minutes every day [20]. The use of Facebook is seen as the most effective communication medium because it can reach new and broader users, while Twitter is seen as the most effective communication medium after Facebook because of speed [20], [28], [29]. The use of Instagram to share the experience of visitors while visiting museums to the broader community through creative multimedia by giving visitors the freedom to capture exhibitions, collections, and activities, then edit the photos and provide hashtags [24], [25].

Museum managers can use social media technology as an online brochure. With the help of social media technology, the museum can be present or accessed online by prospective visitors from various locations to find critical information in preparing for physical visits [30]. Museum managers can re-engineer products and services, then present them through social media to motivate visitors to visit the museum in the future. Museum managers must develop a strategy on how to use internet and social media services to achieve social and economic targets. The use of social media without the right strategy will give a modern impression, but this will have negative consequences for museum managers [31]. Social media is one of the domains of marketing opportunities that are quite interesting in inviting businesses to get involved in internet-based marketing. Businesses increasingly recognize the potential role of social media as a marketing instrument and as a tool for observing and analyzing user behavior. Also, social media can be used by businesses to connect with customers, contribute to customer learning, and get input from customers. Social media is an essential tool for prospective visitors where social media plays a vital role in the decision-making process.

Previous research that examined the relationship between Facebook Fan Page user experience and the Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention has been carried out in the tourism industry [30], [32]–[34]. The research method used in the four studies is quantitative research with the Structural Equation

Model analysis method where the sample used is above 400 respondents. Bilgihan et al. designed a study to investigate the determinant factors of the intention to share information by utilizing a social media platform in the United States [30]. The findings showed that tourist consumption behavior affected by ease of use perception and trust in integrity. Casalo et al. designed a study to investigate the determinant factors that influenced the intentions to use the suggestions from Minube.com, LonelyPlanet, and Trivago in Spain [34]. The intention to use the suggestion was affected by the trust of users that posted advice in the online community website. Attitude toward the online community website was directly affected by the trust in the content and perceptions of usability. Kang & Schuett designed a study to implement the conceptual framework for studying the tourist social media experience when visiting the United States [32]. The success of the intention to share their travel experiences is influenced by social media usage, perceptions of enjoyment, and social media experiences. Leung & Bai designed a study to examine the tourist social media behavior when visiting the hotel in the United States. The findings showed that the intention to revisit was affected by social media [33].

3. METHODS

This study uses a quantitative or positivist approach to observe relationships between variables. In this study using a survey method to obtain data, facts, or information, where each research variable can be described and its influence is known between one variable with another variable.

The hypotheses were tested using multivariate analysis (Structural Equation Modeling). To fulfill the design of this study, the study was conducted in a descriptive and explosive manner. The study was conducted on people who are users of museum social media in Indonesia. The data used in this study are expected to represent the overall behavior of museum social media usage among users. This research was conducted from October 2016 - July 2017.

In this study there are two independent variables namely user motivations (MP) and user expectations (EP). The indicators of user motivation was adopted from the previous studies [35]–[38]. The indicators of user expectation was adopted from the previous studies [30], [35], [39]–[41]. Two moderating variables, namely the

Facebook Fan Page user experience (PPFF) and online community involvement (PKO). The indicators of the Facebook Fan Page user experience was adopted from the previous studies [40], [42], [43]. The indicators of the online community involvement was adopted from the previous studies [44]–[47]. Two mediator variables are the Facebook Fan Page user experience (PPFF) and Facebook Fan Page usage intention (IF). The indicators of the Facebook Fan Page usage intention was adopted from the previous studies [40], [42], [43]. One dependent variable is the Visit Museum Intention. The indicators of the visit museum intention was adopted from the previous studies [2], [20], [38], [43], [44].

Data sources in this study were obtained through two sources, namely: primary data and secondary data. Primary data is collected and obtained from social media users who have become fans or friends on social media managed by museum managers. The data used in this study are expected to present the overall behavior of the use of museum social media in Indonesia.

The primary data collection techniques and secondary data in this study were surveys by distributing questionnaires and observations. The researcher will make an electronic questionnaire with the help of Google Forms and this research survey will be conducted from January 2017 to March 2017 through online media such as Facebook and Whatsapp. The researcher periodically sends invitations to prospective respondents online to fill out questionnaires. Distribution of online questionnaires using Facebook groups museum or Indonesian culture lovers, wall Facebook researchers, fan page museums, and Facebook museum accounts. The observations made in this study were the patterns of behavior of social media users in museums in Indonesia. This activity is carried out through observation of the activities of the museum's social media managers, such as in the form of information dissemination, activities, collections and news and interactions with posts on museum social media in

Indonesia. Observation instruments using Ms. Excel 2016 to record how management of social media by museum managers. The data were analyzed using Amos 20.0.

The population of this study is the Museum Facebook Fan Page users in Indonesia. Since the number of population of this study were difficult to determine, it is difficult to random the Facebook users. In order to get the best results to represent the study, the researchers gather museum Facebook Fan Page and online cultural community groups information. The researchers used random sampling to select the museum Facebook Fan Page and online cultural community Facebook groups for questionnaire distribution. The subjects of this study were individuals who were known to have been followers of museum social media in Indonesia. The sample size in this study were 270 respondents.

Samples taken in the study were obtained through a screening process. Researchers believe that someone who decides to follow the museum's social media is someone who has an interest in the history and culture of Indonesia. The sample selection process is carried out to meet the following criteria: the sample is taken only by museum social media users in Indonesia, the age of the respondent is at least 13 years, social media users must specify at least one museum fan page followed, and geographical location (domicile or work location) in the territory of Indonesia.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The table 1 shows that the user motivations variable consists of five indicators that have a factor loading value of ≥ 0.5 . This shows all indicators of user motivations is valid. It can be concluded that convergent validity has been achieved. The construct reliability value of the user's motivations is 0.712, this value indicates that the motivations construct of the user is reliable. The variance extracted value of user motivations is 0.338, the value indicates that the indicator has a higher error rate.

Table 1 Validity and Reliability of User Motivations

Indicator	Factor Loading	Variance Extracted	Construct Reliability
Express ideas or opinions	0.631		
Communicate with fellow social media users	0.653		
Find friends who share your interests	0.540	0.338	0.712
Relaxation and pleasure in accessing content about the museum	0.565		
Satisfaction and pride in accessing content about the museum	0.507		

Source: Author analysis, 2018

The table 2 shows that the user expectations variable consists of nine indicators which have a factor loading value of ≥ 0.5 . This shows all indicators of user expectations is valid. It can be concluded that convergent validity has been achieved. The value of construct expectations of the

user is 0.847, this value indicates that the construct of user expectations is reliable. The variance extracted value of user expectations is 0.383, the value indicates that the indicator has a higher error rate.

Table 2 Validity And Reliability Of User Expectations

Indicators	Factor Loading	Variance Extracted	Construct Reliability
Accurate content.	0.704		
Latest content.	0.740		
Relevant content.	0.651		
Use the message us feature.	0.576		
Use of event features.	0.552	0.383	0.847
Use the profile information feature.	0.584		
The ease of finding museum information through Facebook.	0.593		
Ease in meeting information needs through Facebook.	0.558		
Helps meet information needs quickly through Facebook.	0.584		

Source: Author analysis, 2018

The table 3 shows that the online community involvement variable consists of three indicators that have a value of factor loading ≥ 0.5 . This shows the indicators of the online community involvement is valid. It can be concluded that convergent validity has been achieved. The construct reliability of the online community

involvement is 0.909, this value indicates that the construct of the online community involvement is reliable. The variance extracted value of the online community involvement is 0.768, this value indicates that the online community involvement construct is valid.

Table 3 Validity And Reliability Of The Online Community Involvement

Indicators	Factor Loading	Variance Extracted	Construct Reliability
Members feel membership in the Facebook group.	0.887		
Members feel ownership in the Facebook group.	0.919	0.768	0.909
Members feel an attachment to the Facebook group.	0.821		

Source: Author analysis, 2018

The table 4 shows that the Facebook Fan Page user experience variable consists of five indicators that have a value of factor loading ≥ 0.5 . This shows the indicators of the Facebook Fan Page user experience is valid. It can be concluded that convergent validity has been achieved. The construct reliability of the Facebook Fan Page user

experience is 0.753, the value indicates that the construct of the Facebook Fan Page user experience is reliable. The variance extracted value of Facebook Fan Page user experience is 0.380, this value indicates that the indicator has a higher error rate.

Table 4 Validity And Reliability Of The Facebook Fan Page User Experience

Indicators	Factor Loading	Variance Extracted	Construct Reliability
Make friends and discuss with fellow cultural lovers.	0.714		
Connect with fellow cultural lovers.	0.608		
Increase knowledge.	0.548	0.380	0.753
Interested in accessing content about the museum.	0.627		
Like content.	0.573		

Source: Author analysis, 2018

The table 5 shows that the Facebook Fan Page usage intention consists of four indicators that have a factor loading value ≥ 0.5 . This shows the indicators of the Facebook Fan Page usage intention is valid. It can be concluded that convergent validity has been achieved. The

construct reliability value of the Facebook Fan Page usage intention is 0.728, the value indicates that the construct of the Facebook Fan Page usage intention is reliable. The variance extracted value of Facebook Fan Page usage intention is 0.401, this

value indicates that the indicator has a higher error rate.

Table 5 Validity And Reliability Of The Facebook Fan Page Usage Intention

Indicators	Factor Loading	Variance Extracted	Construct Reliability
Search for information about the museum.	0.636		
Consider the recommendations of other members.	0.586	0.401	0.728
Share experiences visiting museums.	0.644		
Return to visiting Facebook Fan Page.	0.665		

Source: Author analysis, 2018

The table 6 shows that the visit museum intention consists of three indicators that have a factor loading value ≥ 0.5 . This shows the indicators of the visit museum intention is valid. It can be concluded that convergent validity has been achieved. The construct reliability value is the visit

museum intention is 0.778, the value indicates that the construct of the visit museum intention is reliable. The value of variance extracted the visit museum intention is 0.541, the value indicates that the construct of the visit museum intention is valid.

Table 6 Validity And Reliability Of The Visit Museum Intention

Indicator	Factor Loading	Variance Extracted	Construct Reliability
Strengthen the decision to visit the museum after learning about museum activities on Facebook.	0.719		
Want to visit the museum after learning about museum activities on Facebook.	0.819	0.541	0.778
Want to visit the museum regularly after accessing information about the museum through Facebook	0.659		

Source: Author analysis, 2018

Based on the results of data processing using AMOS, we tested the proposed hypotheses. Hypothesis testing uses the value of t-value with a significance level of 0.05. The t-value in the AMOS

program is a Critical Ratio (C.R.), if the Critical Ratio (C.R.) value is 1.967 or the probability value (P) 0.05 then H0 is rejected (the research hypothesis is accepted).

Figure 1 The Structure Model Results From Amos

The figure 1 is the result of a structural model from Amos, there are 8 significant paths and 1 path that is not significant. The R^2 of Facebook Fan Page usage experience is 0.396. This means that 39.6 percent of the Facebook Fan Page usage experience can be explained by user expectations and user motivations, while 60.4 percent is explained by other. The r^2 of Facebook Fan Page usage intention is 0.446. This means that 44.6

percent of Facebook Fan Page usage intention can be explained by user expectations, user motivations and Facebook Fan Page usage experience, while 55.4 percent is explained by other. The r^2 of visit museum intention is 0.350. This means that 35 percent of the visit museum intention can be explained by the Facebook Fan Page usage intention and the online community involvement, while 65 percent is explained by other factors.

Table 7. Regression Weights: (Group Number 1 – Default Model)

Hypothesis	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Explanation
H-1	0.400	0.055	7.316	***	H-1 Accepted, Significant
H-2	0.059	0.058	1.020	0.308	H-2 Rejected
H-3	0.325	0.055	5.948	***	H-3 Accepted, Significant
H-4	0.159	0.057	2.809	0.005	H-4 Accepted, Significant
H-5	0.516	0.059	8.705	***	H-5 Accepted, Significant
H-6	-0.129	0.037	-3.470	***	H-6 Accepted, Significant
H-7	0.526	0.047	11.240	***	H-7 Accepted, Significant
H-8	0.120	0.036	3.352	0.003	H-8 Accepted, Significant
H-9	-0.071	0.031	-2.296	0.022	H-9 Accepted, Significant

Source: Author analysis, 2018

Table 7 is the summary of hypotheses test result. Based on the results of the first hypothesis test, it shows that there is a significant and positive influence between the users motivation and the Facebook Fan Page usage experience. It can be conclude that the first hypothesis is accepted. The findings in this study supported the previous research findings [32], [33], [35], [43], [48].

Based on the results of the second hypothesis test, it shows that there is no influence between user motivations towards Facebook Fan Page usage intention. It can be conclude that the second hypothesis is rejected. The second hypothesis is rejected because the experience of using Facebook Fan Page is an important aspect that needs to be considered by museum managers, at present museum managers have not managed the museum's Facebook Fan Page properly. The low number and frequency of access to Facebook Fan Page museums that are followed by Facebook users in Indonesia reflects that Facebook users in Indonesia who have an interest in Indonesian culture are less aware of the presence of Facebook Fan Page museums in Indonesia. The findings in this study contrast with previous research regarding the relationship between user motivations towards Facebook Fan Page usage intention [20], [36], [49], [50].

Based on the results of the third hypothesis test, it shows that there is a significant and positive influence between the user expectations and the

Facebook Fan Page usage experience. It can be conclude that the third hypothesis is accepted. The experience of using Facebook Fan Page in museums in Indonesia is influenced by the user expectations which need a useful information, easy access to the information, utilization of Facebook features, and quality content about Indonesian culture. The experience of using Facebook Fan Page provides a clearer interpretation of the relationship between expectations and intentions of using Facebook Fan Page because the indirect influence of user expectations on Facebook Fan Page experience is greater than the direct influence of user expectations on intentions using Facebook Fan Page. The findings in this study support the previous research findings [32], [34], [35], [40], [51].

Based on the results of the fourth hypothesis test, it shows that there is a significant and positive influence between the user expectations and the Facebook Fan Page usage intention. It can be conclude that the fourth hypothesis is accepted. The experience of using Facebook Fan Page is an important aspect that needs to be considered by museum managers because these variables have an indirect influence greater than the direct influence between user expectations and Facebook Fan Page usage intention. Although the current conditions are not very noticeable, this is because museum managers have not managed the Facebook Fan Page properly.

The findings in this study support the previous research findings [30], [34], [39], [41], [42].

Based on the results of the fifth hypothesis test, it shows that there is a significant and positive influence between the Facebook Fan Page usage experience and the Facebook Fan Page usage intention. It can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis is accepted. The intention to use Facebook Fan Museum page is influenced by the respondent experience when using the Facebook Fan Page usage to increase knowledge, get entertainment, and build social relationships with fellow Indonesian culture lovers. The findings in this study support the previous research findings [32], [33], [48].

Based on the results of the sixth hypothesis test, it shows that the online community involvement moderates the relationship between the Facebook Fan Page usage intention and the visit museum intention is significant and negative. It can be concluded that the sixth hypothesis is accepted. The findings in this study contrast to the previous research findings [26], [44], [46], [47], [52]–[55].

Based on the results of the seventh hypothesis test, it is shown that there is a significant and positive influence between Facebook Fan Page usage intention and the visit museum intention, then the seventh hypothesis is accepted. The findings in this study support the previous studies findings [41], [44], [52], [56].

Based on the results of the eighth hypothesis test, it is shown that the Facebook Fan Page usage experience moderates the relationship between user motivations and Facebook Fan Page usage intention is positive and significant. This is an interesting finding because the direct effect of user motivations to the Facebook Fan Page usage intention is not significant, which means the importance of the Facebook Fan Page experience as a moderating factor. This finding in this study is consistent with previous studies [35], [57].

Based on the results of the ninth hypothesis test, it is shown that the Facebook Fan Page experience moderates the relationship between user motivations and Facebook Fan Page usage intention is negative and significant. Respondents involved in this study had a good level of education and profession, and liked to access Facebook. The sophisticated need of respondents to find and get information about the museum through Facebook cannot be fulfilled by the majority of museum managers in Indonesia. The cause is the museum managers in Indonesia do not understand how to develop marketing and communication strategies through social media. Most of the museum

manager's in Indonesia do not have official Facebook Fan Page, the unofficial Facebook Fan Page automatically created by Wikipedia or Facebook if there are visitors who check-in or mention the name of the museum while visiting the museum. The content on this unofficial Facebook Fan Page comes from museum visitors who share their experience of visiting the museum through Facebook and cannot be monitored directly by the museum manager. The museum manager can't evaluate the insight from the visitor's experience which is shared with the unofficial Facebook Fan Page. This finding contrasts to the previous research findings [19], [20], [58], [59].

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the hypotheses testing result, we conclude that eight hypotheses are accepted and one hypothesis is rejected. The accepted hypotheses are there is a significant and positive influence between user motivations and Facebook Fan Page usage experience, there is a significant and positive influence between user expectations and Facebook Fan Page Usage Experience, there is a significant and positive influence between user expectations and Facebook Fan Page usage intention, there is a significant and positive influence between Facebook Fan Page usage experience and Facebook Fan Page usage intention, the online community involvement moderates negatively the relationship between Facebook Fan Page usage intention and the visit museum intention, there is a significant and positive influence between the Facebook Fan Page usage intention and the visit museum intention, there is a moderating effect of the Facebook Fan Page experience between the user's motivations and Facebook Fan Page usage intention, and there is a moderating effect of Facebook Fan Page usage experience between user motivations and Facebook Fan Page usage intention. The rejected hypothesis is the relationship between the user motivations and the Facebook Fan Page usage intention.

The r^2 on the Facebook Fan Page usage intention is 0.446, it means that the intention of using Facebook Fan Page variables can be explained by user expectations, user motivations, and Facebook Fan Page usage experience. The r^2 on the visit museum intention is 0.350, it means that the visit museum intention can be explained by the experience of using Facebook Fan Page and online community involvement.

The contribution of this research is to contribute the Facebook Adoption model that

accommodates the Facebook Fan Page usage experience and the online community involvement for marketing and cultural education in the Museum industry in Indonesia. The research model can be a knowledge reference for academics who want to examine how the behavior of social media users in the museum industry in Indonesia emphasizes the experience of using Facebook Fan Page based on Strategic Experiential Marketing.

The implication of this study is to provide guidance for museum managers regarding the motivations and expectations of users towards using the Facebook Fan Page museum. In addition, the findings of this study can be used by museum managers in developing social media-based marketing strategies to promote and educate museums in accordance with the wishes and needs of the community.

The limitation of this study is that museum managers have not managed the Facebook Fan Page properly. The low number and frequency of access to Facebook Fan Page museums that are followed by Facebook users in Indonesia reflects that Facebook users in Indonesia who have an interest in Indonesian culture are less aware of the presence of Facebook Fan Page museums in Indonesia. In addition, museum managers in Indonesia do not yet understand how to develop marketing and communication strategies through social media. Most of the museum manager's presence in Indonesia on Facebook still uses the Unofficial Facebook Fan Page, the page will be automatically created by Wikipedia or Facebook if there are visitors who check-in or mention the name of the museum while visiting the museum.

Further research can discuss how to implement a good museum marketing and education strategy so that people are aware of the presence of museums in cyberspace and are interested in visiting museums in the future. Future research needs to consider how the experience of using Instagram and Twitter in museums. The use of Instagram is very good for sharing the experience of visits through media images and videos and the use of Twitter is very good to accelerate the dissemination of information about the museum through short messages. Future research needs to combine the experience of on-site and online visits to enrich the factors that influence the intention of visiting museums in Indonesia.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Digitalbuzz, "SlideShare: Global Digital Statistics For 2016," 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://www.digitalbuzzblog.com/slideshare-global-digital-statistics-report-for-2016/>. [Accessed: 07-Jun-2016].
- [2] I. G. B. R. Utama, "Mengelola Warisan Budaya Sebagai Produk Pariwisata," Researchgate, 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.yayasankertagama.org/article/artic le3.pdf>. [Accessed: 13-Mar-2017].
- [3] UNESCO, "Towards Sustainable Strategies for Creative Tourism," 2008.
- [4] Kemendikbud, Undang-Undang Nomor 5 Tahun 2017 Tentang Pemajuan Kebudayaan. 2017.
- [5] A. A. A. Wulandari, A. A. S. Fajarwati, and F. Latif, "The Relationship of Exhibition Space Design and the Success of Delivering Messages to Museum Visitors in Jakarta," *Humaniora*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 219, Oct. 2017.
- [6] R. T. Sulistiyana, D. Hamid, and D. F. Azizah, "Pengaruh Fasilitas Wisata dan Harga Terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen (Studi pada Museum Satwa)," *J. Adm. Bisnis*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2015.
- [7] E. A. Kurnia, "Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan, Harga, dan Promosi Terhadap Kepuasan Pengunjung di Museum Ronggowarsito Semarang," Universitas Dian Nuswantoro, 2014.
- [8] D. A. M. Jannah, N. Andriani, and M. Arief, "Pengaruh Strategi Experiential Marketing Terhadap Kepuasan Pengunjung Museum Sepuluh Nopember Surabaya," *J. Stud. Manaj. Dan Bisnis*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 53–64, 2014.
- [9] I. D. S. Dhiba and A. Maduwinarti, "Analisis Pengaruh Bauran Pemasaran Jasa Terhadap Minat Pengunjung Pada Obyek Wisata Museum Kesehatan Dr. Adhyatma, MPH Surabaya," *J. Ilmu Ekon. Manaj.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 94–109, 2014.
- [10] S. Marwa and F. Rahmafritria, "A Factor Analysis of Visitors' Motivation in Visiting the Geology Museum of Bandung," *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.*, vol. 145, no. 1, p. 012084, Apr. 2018.
- [11] R. D. G. Kamilanovy and Suwatno, "Meningkatkan Loyalitas Pengunjung Museum Konferensi Asia Afrika Melalui Brand Community Sahabat Museum (Survei Terhadap Member Sahabat Museum

- Konperensi Asia Afrika),” *Tour. Hosp. Essentials J.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 671–692, 2013.
- [12] B. Widjajanta and G. I. W. Avrianti, “Keputusan Mengunjungi Museum Negeri Sri Baduga Bandung,” *Strategic*, vol. 8, no. 15, pp. 1–16, 2009.
- [13] W. Dirgantara, “Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan dan Nilai Pelanggan Terhadap Kepuasan Pengunjung Museum Kartini Jepara,” *Manag. Anal. J.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 110–117, 2013.
- [14] K. A. E. Harahap, “Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan, Harga, dan Promosi Terhadap Kepuasan Pengunjung di Museum Ronggowarsito Semarang,” 2014.
- [15] N. Magetsari, “Museum di Era Pascamodern,” in *Seminar Towards Indonesian Postmodern Museums*, 2011, pp. 1–14.
- [16] Kemdikbud, “Laporan Akuntabilitas Kinerja Instansi Pemerintah (LAKIP) Dirjen Kemdikbud 2012,” Jakarta, 2012.
- [17] Kemdikbud, “Laporan Akuntabilitas Kinerja Instansi Pemerintah (LAKIP) Dirje Kemdikbud 2014,” Jakarta, 2014.
- [18] D. Sulistyowati, “Strategi Edukasi Museum dan Pemasarannya: Studi Kasus Museum Sejarah Jakarta,” in *Seminar Towards Indonesian Postmodern Museums*, 2011, pp. 1–19.
- [19] D. Peacock, “Making Ways for Change: Museums, Disruptive Technologies and Organisational Change,” *Museum Manag. Curatorsh.*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 333–351, 2008.
- [20] P. Klimpel, “Where do Museums Stand in the Digital Age? Private Companies, Heritage Institutions and the Civil Society,” in *Museums in the Digital Age: Museums and the Development of Active Citizenship*, 2013, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 9–12.
- [21] A. M. Sundjaja and E. Ekawati, “Evaluation of edutainment e-marketing model implementation at Bank Mandiri Museum,” in *2015 International Seminar on Intelligent Technology and Its Applications, ISITIA 2015 - Proceeding*, 2015, pp. 341–344.
- [22] M. Skov, “The Reinvented Museum: Exploring Information Seeking Behaviour in a Digital Museum Context,” 2009.
- [23] M. Arends, D. Goldfarb, D. Merkl, and M. Weingartner, “Museums on the Web,” *Handb. Res. Technol. Cult. Herit.*, pp. 142–165, 2011.
- [24] A. Fletcher and M. J. Lee, “Current Social Media Uses and Evaluations in American Museums,” *Museum Manag. Curatorsh.*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 505–521, 2012.
- [25] A. Hausmann, “The Importance of Word of Mouth for Museums: An Analytical Framework,” *Int. J. Arts Manag.*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 32–43, 2008.
- [26] A. H. Cornellia, H. S. A. Putra, T. K. Priyambodo, and Y. A. Widyaningsih, “Social Media Based Proposed Model for Museum Marketing Strategy in Yogyakarta,” *Adv. Sci. Lett.*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 10636–10639, Nov. 2017.
- [27] H. Q. Vu, J. M. Luo, B. H. Ye, G. Li, and R. Law, “Evaluating museum visitor experiences based on user-generated travel photos,” *J. Travel Tour. Mark.*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 493–506, May 2018.
- [28] A. Weilenmann, T. Hillman, and B. Jungselius, “Instagram at the museum: Communicating the museum experience through social photo sharing,” in *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2013, no. April 2013, pp. 1843–1852.
- [29] S. Mayasari and C. Indraswari, “Efektivitas Media Sosial Instagram Dalam Publikasi HUT Museum Nasional Indonesia (MNI) Kepada Masyarakat,” *J. Komun.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 190–196, Sep. 2018.
- [30] J. K. Ayeh, N. Au, and R. Law, “Do We Believe in TripAdvisor? Examining Credibility Perceptions and Online Travelers’ Attitude toward Using User-Generated Content,” *J. Travel Res.*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 437–452, Jul. 2013.
- [31] M. Pérez-Sanagustín, D. Parra, R. Verdugo, G. García-Galleguillos, and M. Nussbaum, “Using QR codes to increase user engagement in museum-like spaces,” *Comput. Human Behav.*, vol. 60, pp. 73–85, Jul. 2016.
- [32] K. Charitonos, C. Blake, E. Scanlon, and A. Jones, “Museum learning via social and mobile technologies: (How) can online interactions enhance the visitor experience?,” *Br. J. Educ. Technol.*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 802–819, 2012.
- [33] T. Moussouri and G. Roussos, “Examining the Effect of Visitor Motivation on Observed Visit Strategies Using Mobile Computer Technologies,” *Visit. Stud.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 21–38, 2013.
- [34] A. Bilgihan, A. Barreda, F. Okumus, and K. Nusair, “Consumer perception of knowledge-sharing in travel-related Online Social Networks,” *Tour. Manag.*, vol. 52, pp. 287–296, 2016.
- [35] A. Padilla-Meléndez and A. R. Del Águila-Obra, “Web and social media usage by

- museums: Online value creation,” *Int. J. Inf. Manage.*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 892–898, 2013.
- [36] M. Kang and M. a Schuett, “Determinants of Sharing Travel Experiences in Social Media,” *J. Travel Tour. Mark.*, vol. 30, no. 1, p. 107, 2013.
- [37] X. Y. Leung and B. Bai, “How Motivation, Opportunity, and Ability Impact Travelers’ Social Media Involvement and Revisit Intention,” *J. Travel Tour. Mark.*, vol. 30, no. February 2015, pp. 58–77, 2013.
- [38] L. V. Casalo, C. Flavián, and M. Guinalú, “Understanding the intention to follow the advice obtained in an online travel community,” *Comput. Human Behav.*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 622–633, Mar. 2011.
- [39] K. Heinonen, “Consumer Activity in Social Media: Managerial Approaches to Consumers’ Social Media Behavior,” *J. Consum. Behav.*, vol. 10, pp. 356–364, 2011.
- [40] G. Chen, S. Yang, and S. Tang, “Sense of virtual community and knowledge contribution in a P3 virtual community: Motivation and experience,” *Internet Res.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 4–26, Jan. 2013.
- [41] J. Tang and Q. Chenyu, “Research on Motivation, Experience, Satisfaction and Behavioral Intention of Museum Tourism — A Case of Macau Museum,” in *Tourism and Hospitality Development Between China and EU*, S. Guo, Ed. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2015, pp. 137–153.
- [42] W.-H. S. Tsai and L. R. Men, “Motivations and Antecedents of Consumer Engagement With Brand Pages on Social Networking Sites,” *J. Interact. Advert.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 76–87, 2013.
- [43] M.-H. Hsu, S.-W. Tien, H.-C. Lin, and C.-M. Chang, “Understanding the Roles of Cultural Differences and Socio-Economic Status in Social Media Continuance Intention,” *Inf. Technol. People*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 224–241, Mar. 2015.
- [44] A. E. M. I. Adam and S. B. Brahim, “Sudanese Marketing Practitioners Motives’ towards Adopting Social Media Technology in marketing activities: the Mediating role of Intention and Moderating effect of experience,” *Sudan University of Science and Technology*, 2016.
- [45] W. Lee, L. Xiong, and C. Hu, “The effect of Facebook users’ arousal and valence on intention to go to the festival: Applying an extension of the technology acceptance model,” *Int. J. Hosp. Manag.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 819–827, 2012.
- [46] K. Sookhanaphibarn, U. Chatuporn, and K. N. Nakornphanom, “User Modeling on Social Media for Art Museums and Galleries,” in *Social Computing and Social Media, 7th International Conference, SCSM 2015, Held as Part of HCI International 2015, Los Angeles, CA, USA, August 2-7, 2015, Proceedings, 1st ed.*, G. Meiselwitz, Ed. Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 89–95.
- [47] H.-C. Chen, C.-C. Hsu, C.-H. Chang, and Y.-M. Huang, “Applying the Technology Acceptance Model to Evaluate the Learning Companion Recommendation System on Facebook,” in *Proceedings - 2012 IEEE 4th International Conference on Technology for Education, T4E 2012*, 2012, no. 1, pp. 160–163.
- [48] R. Filieri and F. McLeay, “E-WOM and Accommodation: An Analysis of the Factors That Influence Travelers’ Adoption of Information from Online Reviews,” *J. Travel Res.*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 44–57, Jan. 2014.
- [49] Y. Zheng, K. Zhao, and A. Stylianou, “The impacts of information quality and system quality on users’ continuance intention in information-exchange virtual communities: An empirical investigation,” *Decis. Support Syst.*, vol. 56, pp. 513–524, Dec. 2013.
- [50] G. Agag and A. A. El-Masry, “Understanding consumer intention to participate in online travel community and effects on consumer intention to purchase travel online and WOM: An integration of innovation diffusion theory and TAM with trust,” *Comput. Human Behav.*, vol. 60, pp. 97–111, Jul. 2016.
- [51] A. Kavoura and A. Stavrianea, “Following and Belonging to an Online Travel Community in Social Media, its Shared Characteristics and Gender Differences,” *Procedia - Soc. Behav. Sci.*, vol. 175, pp. 515–521, Feb. 2015.
- [52] P. Racherla and W. Friske, “Perceived ‘usefulness’ of online consumer reviews: An exploratory investigation across three services categories,” *Electron. Commer. Res. Appl.*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 548–559, Nov. 2012.
- [53] M. Kim and M. Lee, “Effects of review characteristics and consumer regulatory focus on perceived review usefulness,” *Soc. Behav. Pers.*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 1319–1334, Sep. 2015.

- [54] A. M. Munar and J. K. S. Jacobsen, “Trust and Involvement in Tourism Social Media and Web-Based Travel Information Sources,” *Scand. J. Hosp. Tour.*, vol. 13, no. January 2015, pp. 1–19, Apr. 2013.
- [55] M. S. Ahmad and N. B. Abu Talib, “Analysis of Community Empowerment on Projects Sustainability: Moderating Role of Sense of Community,” *Soc. Indic. Res.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 235–246, Dec. 2014.
- [56] J. Brown, A. J. Broderick, and N. Lee, “Word of mouth communication within online communities: Conceptualizing the online social network,” *J. Interact. Mark.*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 2–20, Jan. 2007.
- [57] Y. S. Hau and Y. G. Kim, “Why Would Online Gamers Share Their Innovation-Conducive Knowledge in the Online Game User Community? Integrating Individual Motivations and Social Capital Perspectives,” *Comput. Human Behav.*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 956–970, Mar. 2011.
- [58] S. Tsaor, Y. Chiu, and C. Wang, “The Visitors Behavioral Consequences of Experiential Marketing The Visitors Behavioral Consequences of Experiential Marketing: An Empirical Study on Taipei Zoo,” *J. Travel Tour. Mark.*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 37–41, 2007.
- [59] L. Solima, “Digital Resources and Approaches Adopted by User-Centred Museums,” *Handb. Res. Manag. Cult. Prod.*, pp. 181–199, 2016.
- [60] R. Srinivasan, R. Boast, J. Furner, and K. M. Becvar, “Digital Museums and Diverse Cultural Knowledges: Moving Past the Traditional Catalog,” *Inf. Soc.*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 265–278, 2009.